

NAMING PRINCIPLES OF MICROTOPYMS OF KUMKURGAN DISTRICT

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Abstract: This article talks about the naming principles of microtoponyms of Kumkurgan district of Surkhandarya region.

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Kumkurgan is located on the banks of the ancient "Great Silk Road" on the banks of the river, in a convenient region for residents to live in. How many times have Iranian Ahmonites, Alexander the Great, Tokharistan, Kushan kings, Chaganian emirs, It is the land where the Arab conquerors, Samanids, Ghaznavids, Karakhanids, Seljuks, Khorezmshahs stopped and showed bravery against them.

Analyzing the microtoponyms of this land, we would like to draw attention to the fact that the names of these places contain a lot of information about the ancient history, the geography of this place, the characteristics of the language in the past period. The historical-archaeological-ethnographic scientific research conducted by our scientists proved that the settlement of the population in this area has a history of 2000 years. Those who lived in the valleys and engaged in pottery were called "Khumkharons". According to this, the scientist came to the conclusion that perhaps Khumkharan later took the form of Kumkurgan. In fact, the meaning of the word Kunqurgan is a house on a sandy hill, a small hillock, a destination, surrounded by sand, steppe, soil. means a fortification surrounded by...

In the translation of the book "Dastur ul-muluk" by Hoja Samandar Termizi, written by the literary scholar Jabbor Esanov in the years 1678-1740, it is mentioned that the writer lived and created in the villages of Takto`gai, Kapto`gai, Jalair in the Kumkurgan region. So it is mentioned in the literary book of toponyms in the Kumkurgan region of the XVI-XVII centuries: "This place took the Kumkurgan fortress as its home. He harvested the reeds, dried the water in the forest, opened up a lot of irrigated land, and started cattle breeding and farming. The villages of Takto`gai, Kapto`gai, Bedov togai, Jaloyir, and Karvontushdi mentioned in the book correspond to the territory of Kumkurgan.

These villages still exist today, and according to the locals, these villages were built in the place of forests. In the 17th-19th centuries, Kurgan Ovul, Zartepa, Qorovultepa, Munchogtepa, Kumtepa, Kumqo were located in the district. The toponyms of Rgan Ovul, Khojamulki, Zarkamar, and Tolliqoir were widely used. At the end of the 19th century, the toponyms of Arpapoya, Mingtut, Kapcho`gai, Kakaydi, Jaloyir, Kumkurgan, Oqkapchigai, Khojamulki were used in sources. Today, almost all of these place names have been preserved. In particular, the Kumkurgan district located in the Surkhan oasis was under the rule of the Ashtarkhanids from the 16th century until 1753. Since 1753, the territory of the Surkhandarya region, including Kumkurgan, was part of the Bukhara Khanate. There are names of valleys, lakes, a number of ancient places, castles, ruins, and hills, and there are various interpretations and hypotheses in science about their reasons, meanings, origin (etymology). Samarkand, Bukhara, Ko`kan, Names such as Termiz, Urgut, Namangan are products of very ancient times, their meaning and language are based on the thoughts and ideas of our ancestors who lived in the distant past, and some that are sufficiently known and unknown to us now. Linguistic elements of dead languages are embodied. Researches of linguists in the emergence of toponyms in the territory of Uzbekistan include the ancient Khorezm language, ancient Iranian languages, ancient Sog, in addition to the ancient Turkic (Uzbek) language. It shows the participation of Sanskrit, Chinese, Indian, Greek, and Mongolian languages. Therefore, the toponyms, in turn, are the roots of a number of ancient, including dead languages, known and unknown to us. It is also a unique source that expresses and preserves Avian linguistic samples. Similar toponyms can be found in place names in Kumkurgan district... For example, Katman (Sogdian), Baldir (ancient Turkic), Kapchagai (Mongolian), Bandikhon (elements of the ancient Iranian language)

There are many toponyms. The meanings of many toponyms are currently unknown to us. The more complex the name is, the more incomprehensible and unknown its meaning is for us now, the more ancient and old the word is. Thus, place names, on the one hand, are famous names of certain objects, very old words, and on the other hand, they contain valuable information about the history of the people, the natural and geographical environment of the country. It is also a rare resource.

So, toponyms are like a rare chest that tells us about the signs and characteristics of ancient languages that are known or unknown to us, keeping them in itself and preserving them over time.

In conclusion, it should be said that the name of Kumkurgan district did not appear only yesterday. This name has been formed for centuries and has reached its current state after passing through centuries. The example of Kumkurgan

district shows that the name of a part of our republic is not in vain, it has its own reasons, and its place in our future life is very important.

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The victory of the October revolution in 1917 and the Bukhara revolution of September 2, 1920, the emir of Bukhara, Said Olimkhan, was overthrown and the Soviet Republic of Bukhara was established. There were fierce battles for the Soviet power in the rivers of Okkapchigai. From 1925, Kumkurgan and Khojamulki village revolutionary committees were formed. At that time, it was considered the largest among the surrounding villages of Shamoli, Yakhasboy, Chayontepa and Aylanma. In 1924, national-administrative demarcation was carried out in Central Asia. In 1929, as in other parts of the Soviet Union, there was a radical change in Kumkurgan district. In 1929, 25 collective farms were established in the district. Kolkhozes such as Red Farmer, Budyonny, Ulyanov, Molotov, Frunze, Red Soldier, Voroshilov, Red Banner, Zarbdor, Kuybyshev, Lenin, Kalinin, Zhdanov, Komsomol, Red October, Moscow were established (these collective farm names are examples of official toponyms) During the time of the Soviets, most of these toponymic names were named by instructions and special decisions from above. given, the name does not have any connection with the properties of the object it is referring to, and these were toponyms that did not have a nominative basis. Their selection and placement were not determined by the conditions related to the natural features of the place, place, or object, but by ideological and ideological views that were not materially and naturally related to the name. most of them were names given to the names of individuals. For example, the Kuibyshev, Voroshilov, Kalinin, Frunze, Molotov, Budyonny, Ulyanov collective farms located in Kumkurgan district can be cited as an example. Place names are a component of the country's culture. `lib, the name of each place - This is a part of the ancient history, the distant past of that place.

On October 21, 1989, the Law on the State Language was adopted. In Article 24 of this law, "...all historical names and names of places are considered the national property of the people and are protected by the state." " was shown.

This was the restoration of the sacred and great history of the Uzbek people, the realization of national feelings, dreams and hopes, the opportunity for the name of the Motherland, the people, the mirror of the nation to be known to the world and to think freely. In the first years of independence, important works and activities were carried out to restore toponyms nationally, to name places and regions reflecting national traditions and values. On December 21, 1995, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a decision on amendments and

additions to the Law on the State Language of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "The names of cities and geographical objects will be reflected in the state language" was added. On August 30, 1996, in the law "On the procedure for resolving issues of administrative-territorial structure, naming and changing names of toponymic objects in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "... administrative-territorial units, population comprehensive works were carried out according to the instructions of "determines the procedure for naming and changing the names of centers and their components, as well as enterprises, institutions, organizations, physical-geographical, geological, and other objects." the instructions showed that toponyms are the ancient material and spiritual heritage of the people's spirituality, special attention was paid to the issue of educating the current young generation and leaving a worthy legacy for the next generation, enriching national values. During the years of independence, restoration of historical toponyms, national language and policy of fair treatment of national values is carried out y entered. In particular, in Kumkurgan district, the works of changing place names and restoring historical place names reflecting national values and customs were carried out. As a result, the Komsomol thirty-year state farm in the district was changed to the Besh Kahramon collective farm, the Gagarin state farm to the Saikhan collective farm, the Moskva collective farm to the Safar Boymatov collective farm.

After our republic gained independence, toponyms began to be restored in the manner of national values. As a result, the names of about 20,360 persons in the Surkhandarya region, which did not comply with the legal documents and nameless geographical objects, were renamed with the participation of regional toponymic commissions. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev History of the Surkhan oasis,

He pays special attention to the history of the oasis, which made a worthy contribution to the development of world civilization due to the study of its ethnography and archeology, its great figures, and the invaluable services of its scholars and saints to the worldly and religious thinking. Since the independence of our republic, names such as "Independence, Independence, Nurli Dayar, Hurriyat, Elabad, Mehrabad, New Life, New Generation" have appeared in Kumkurgan district, praising the independence of our country.

The study of toponymic terms provides valuable information not only for onomastics, but also for the sciences of geography, geology, and biology. He paid attention to the unique features of the history of Hna. Place names are formed as a result of the great service of the people's spirituality and are passed from generation to generation. Therefore, attention to place names is attention to the Motherland, the nation.

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